

Study of the Law on Child Protection from Cases of Verbal Violence Against Children

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ABSTRACT

Cases of violence against children in the modern era are currently very common. Cases of violence against children are committed by adults. Law enforcement for someone who is confronted needs to be done for the sake of upholding the law. An action committed against violence against children has a cause which is the background to why the action was carried out. This is where the important role of criminology is in knowing why someone commits a crime and how to overcome the crime problem. The role of the family and society is very important to monitor violence against children.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country of law in accordance with the mandate of the 1945 Law Article 1 Paragraph 3. The consequence of being a country of law is that every action must be appropriate and in accordance with permitted and prohibited actions. All kinds of criminal acts in Indonesia are regulated in law, both those committed by adults and criminal acts committed by small children.

Several experts stated that the criminological causes of verbal violence in children, apart from external factors, greatly influence children's cognitive development in social interactions between parents and children. In fact, children must be protected according to Law no. 23 of 2002 concerning child protection, beatings and abuse. Young children experience more stress than other generations. The school environment is one of the things that makes children stressed because the teacher's attitude towards children is also one of them. As for parents against children, verbal violence can occur, sometimes if the child is very annoying in the opinion of the parents. The role of parents and teachers in their environment plays a very important role in children's development from an early age until they grow into adulthood. In this journal, criminological studies of cases of verbal violence against children will be discussed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Verbal Abuse Against Children

Understanding Verbal Violence/Abuse

Verbal violence is violence carried out through speech such as shouting, cursing, insulting, ridiculing, shouting, slandering and speaking harshly and humiliating in public with harsh words. The expert opinion regarding verbal violence is: Various utterances aimed at hurting children will affect them either directly or indirectly because children will always consider themselves to be the same as the words spoken (Choirunnisa, 2008). Insulting and condescending words will be absorbed into the child's memory, as a result, they will lose their self-confidence and spur their parents' anger, ultimately giving rise to a feeling of revenge which can affect their way of socializing (Irwanto, 2000). Verbal Abuse or also called emotional child abuse is a verbal action or behavior that causes detrimental consequences. Verbal Abuse occurs when parents tell the child to be quiet or not to cry, if the child wants to talk, the parents continually say harsh words to the child such as, don't be noisy, don't cry, and so on. The child can absorb this into his memory. From the opinion above, it can be taken to mean that verbal violence towards children is violence perpetrated by parents/adults against children with harsh words, ridiculing, cursing, slandering or using humiliating harsh words whether it occurs in public or between other people old man and child.

Understanding Early Childhood

Early childhood is a child aged between 0 (zero) - 8 (eight) years. According to Beichler and Snowman (Dwi Yulianti, 2010:7) what is called early childhood is a child aged between 3 (three) - 6 (six) years, the essence of early

childhood (August, 2012) is a unique individual who has growth and development in cognitive, physical, social emotional, language and artistic/creativity aspects that are appropriate to the stage of development they are going through. The development of each child is different, this is due to nutritional intake and stimulation provided by parents. Intensive stimulation from the environment makes children able to carry out their developmental tasks well.

Types or Forms of Verbal Violence/Abuse

1. Sewearing at children

Harsh words from adults or from a child's parents towards a child can result in the child having an impact on the child's psychological development. This will cause a bad impact on the child.

2. Mocking children

By ridiculing a child, the child may become inferior and find it difficult to develop. On the other hand, parents should not ridicule them, but should promote and encourage their children to grow. Saying something demeaning to a child can disrupt the development of the child's psychological health.

Verbal violence usually does not have physical consequences for the child, but the child can be damaged for years to come. The consequences of verbal violence cause very deep wounds to children, more than rape (Soetjningsih, 2002). Psychological effects due to verbal violence on children (Ria, 2008; Widysatuti: 2006). Aggressive parents can give birth to aggressive children who will later become cruel and aggressive too. Mental disorders are mental disorders related to bad treatment received when they, in this case the child, were still small.

METHODOLOGY

This research method is library research which is called library research with data obtained from the library with data obtained from the library in the form of encyclopedias, theses, theses, dissertations, books, journals, documents, dictionaries, etc. Magazine (Khatibah, 2013). The procedure for this research literature is to have a topic, look for information related to the topic in the form of related journals, and prepare a report. As for the data sources for this research, namely from literature in the form of relevant journals consisting of two journals that have variables that are appropriate to the research topic. The data collection technique in this research is documentation, namely searching for data regarding variables in the form of articles or journals.

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

Herlina (2016), regarding the relationship between level of knowledge and verbal abuse behavior between parents and children in Kuwon Sidomulyo Hamlet, Bambanglipuro, Bantul, Yogyakarta, stated that the results of the Kendall Tau analysis test obtained a calculated value of 0.215 with a significant value of 0.029, which is smaller than the p-value, so there is a level relationship. Knowledge of parents' verbal violent behavior towards children. Based on research regarding the relationship between parental knowledge and verbal violence behavior in children according to the Kendall Tau statistical test with a small p-value of 0.05, namely 0.016 in research conducted by Leony (2017) on the Relationship between Parental Knowledge and Behavior. Verbal Violence in Children.

Based on research results from several journals taken, it was found that there are various factors that can cause parents to commit verbal violence against children. In research (Sari, 2014) regarding the relationship between incidents of parental verbal violence towards children and the cognitive development of preschool aged children in Tarok Dipo Village with 67 respondents, it was found that 46.3% (31 people) experienced incidents of verbal violence. This shows that there are still incidents of verbal violence perpetrated by parents against children.

In this case, the role of parents is very important in the child's growth during their growth period, lest negative information can be absorbed by the child which can hinder the child's growth and development.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on some of this research, it can be concluded that there are forms of verbal violence from parents towards children.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

None of this research is perfect, because every study has limitations. Therefore, constructive suggestions are needed for future progress.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Study of the Law on Child Protection from Cases of Verbal Violence Against Children".

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